

SDS-PAGE characterization of green-stemmed and red-stemmed *Basella alba* L.

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ABSTRACT

The characterization of species by electrophoresis has played significant roles in delimiting species over the years. In this study, the leaves and seeds obtained from matured green-stemmed and red-stemmed *Basella alba* were characterized using Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate (SDS-PAGE) Polyacrylamide Gel Electrophoresis (PAGE) with a view to investigate their taxonomic status. Data obtained revealed high level of similarity in the seed and leaf protein profile of the two *Basella* morphotypes studied. The study revealed relatively high level of coefficient of similarity between the green stemmed and the red stemmed *Basella alba* studied, with the seed protein having 50% and the leaf protein having 75% similarity, indicating that a strong degree of similarity exist between the green stemmed and the red stemmed *Basella alba* studied irrespective of their stem colors. Five common bands were found between the seed protein of the green stemmed and red stemmed *B. alba* studied at 0.2cm – 0.4cm, 4.3 – 4.8 cm, 4.8 – 5.2, 5.5 cm – 5.8 cm, and 6.0 cm – 6.5 cm. The red stemmed *B. alba* seed protein had 2 unique bands at 2.6 cm – 3.2 cm and 3.6 cm – 4.3 cm, while the green stemmed had 3 unique bands at 2.8 cm – 3.2 cm, 5.2 cm – 5.3 cm, and 6.4 cm – 6.5 cm. Six common bands were found in the leaf protein of the two *B.alba* morphotypes studied at 2.3 – 2.6 cm, 4.5 cm – 4.8 cm, 5.0 – 5.4 cm, 6.0 cm – 6.3 cm, 6.4 cm – 6.5 cm, and 6.5 cm – 6.6 cm. The red-stemmed *Basella alba* leaf had one (1) unique band at 0.2cm – 0.4cm, while the green-stemmed *Basella alba* leaf had one (1) unique band at 0.1cm. The study supported the taxonomic classification of the green stemmed and red stemmed *B.alba* as morphotypes or varieties belonging to same species.

KEY WORDS: *Basella alba*, Electrophoretic characterization, Evolutionary relationship, Protein bands

INTRODUCTION

The green-stemmed and red-stemmed *Basella alba* are vigorous, fast-growing, heat-tolerant, perennial tropical vines (Chaurasiya *et al.*, 2021; Tănase *et al.*, 2020). They belong to the family Basellaceae (Bolaji *et al.*, 2022a; Bose *et al.*, 2023). *Basella alba* flowers are sessile, white with pink tips, freely arranged in long-stalked spikes. The green-stemmed and red-stemmed *B. alba* differ mainly in stem coloration and some floral and fruit traits (Deshmukh & Gaikwad, 2020; Bolaji *et al.*, 2022b; Bolaji *et al.*, 2023). *Basella alba* is widely cultivated as an annual leafy vegetable and also grown as an ornamental vine (Tănase *et al.*, 2020). It is popular in many tropical regions, including southern and northern Nigeria, where the leaves are cooked as vegetables and used in soups (Bose *et al.*, 2023; Bolaji *et al.*, 2022c; Adegoke & Ojo, 2017). The leaves are rich in vitamins, minerals, mucilage, and antioxidants, giving the plant nutritional and functional food value (Kumar *et al.*, 2021; Zhang *et al.*, 2024).

Pharmacological studies of *B. alba* have demonstrated significant analgesic (antinociceptive), anti-ulcer/gastroprotective, antioxidant, anti-proliferative, and anti-angiogenic activities of *B. alba* extracts (Sheik *et al.*, 2023; Halayal *et al.*, 2025). Comprehensive phytochemical and ethnomedicinal reviews also confirm numerous traditional uses and pharmacological activities of *B. alba*, including antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, wound-healing, anti-ulcer, and fertility-related properties (Bose *et al.*, 2021; Madhavi *et al.*, 2023).

Electrophoresis-based characterization of seeds and other plant parts have been utilized by researchers in revealing interparental and interspecific diversity, phylogenetic relationships, and trait associations, and gel-based proteomics remains a valuable complement to newer methods (Pandey *et al.*, 2025). There exist some inconsistencies in the taxonomic classification of the green stemmed and the red stemmed *B. alba*, with some researchers regarding them as being synonymous, some as separate species, while others regard them as varieties (Warrier *et al.*, 1996; Larkcom, 2007; Oladele and Aborishade, 2009; Roy *et al.*, 2010; Bolaji *et al.*, 2022a). The objective of this study was therefore to characterize the two *Basella* forms using SDS PAGE, so as to provide useful information that could assist in understanding their taxonomic relationship.

METHODOLOGY

SDS PAGE was carried out on the crude proteins extracted from the seeds and leaf of mature green-stemmed and red-stemmed *Basella alba* obtained from Ile-Ife (7 30'42.3"N 4 32' 51.2"E), Osun State, Nigeria following the method of Oladejo *et al.* (2019). The procedure was carried out in the Biotechnology Laboratory, Department of Animal Sciences, Faculty of Agriculture, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.

0.8 g of the plant samples (leaves and seeds separately) were washed with distilled water and macerated with sterile mortar and pestle in 0.8% phosphate buffered saline (PBS) containing 0.4 M NaCl at pH 8.0. The extract was centrifuged at 5,000 rpm for 10 min and the supernatant of each sample was collected. 15 µl of each of the extract was subjected to electrophoresis in 12% polyacrylamide gel. Gels were stained with 0.3 % Coomassie brilliant blue. De-staining in methanol, acetic acid and distilled water (1:3:5 v/v) was done overnight to reveal the protein bands for scoring

Seven percent (7%) of B-mercaptoethanol (Sigma) in sample buffer was used for the preparation of each of the plant samples under a fume hood. A discontinuous system of employing 12% separation gel overlaid with a 4% stacking gel was adopted. Sample buffer and B-mercaptoethanol was added in addition to 30µl of high molecular and low molecular weight protein markers following the method of Omitogun *et al.*, 1999. The samples were heated at 95 °C for 5 min in a water bath. 25 µl of the heated sample was added to the prepared SDS PAGE gels and sample buffer with 40% sucrose solution being loaded in each well. The separation of protein was carried out with the use of Bio-Rad Electrophoresis Power Supply Model 200/2.0 in the Bio-Rad Mini Protean 11 Cell at 150 Volts for 55 min. The gels were stained with 0.3% Coomassie Brilliant blue for 18 hours. The gels were scanned with HP 3320 scanner and the images stored for scoring.

Data were collected on the scanned gels by scoring the presence (1) or absence (0) of protein bands directly from the computer screen. The protein bands on each gel were compared with the known molecular weights (kDa) of the standard. The similarity coefficient was then calculated following the methods of Sneath and Sokal (1973)

as follows:

$$\text{Coefficient of similarity (CS)} = \frac{a}{a+b+c} * 100$$

Where CS = coefficient of similarity between species 1 & 2

a = number of bands common to 1 and 2

b = number of bands in 1, not in 2

c = number of bands in 2, not in 1

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RESULTS

A close examination of the protein profile of the seed and leaf protein of the *Basella alba* studied (Figures 1 and 2) revealed that the variation in the protein bands observed in this study were mostly qualitative, having to do with the thickness of the bands and staining intensity.

The SDS PAGE of the seed protein led to the detection of fifteen (15) bands, two (2) of which were slow moving, three (3) were intermediate, and ten (10) were fast moving (Table 1). The study revealed that for the seed protein, the green stemmed *B. alba* had a total of eight (8) bands, while the red stemmed had seven (7) bands (Table 1).

Figure 1: Electrophoregram of the seed and leaf protein of the green-stemmed and red-stemmed *Basella alba* studied

M: Protein standard; A: Red-stemmed *Basella alba* seed; B: Red-stemmed *Basella alba* leaf; C: Green-stemmed *Basella alba* seed; D: Green-stemmed *Basella alba* leaf.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of the electrophoregram of the seed and leaf protein of the green-stemmed and red-stemmed *Basella alba* studied.

A: Red-stemmed *Basella alba* seed; B: Red-stemmed *Basella alba* leaf; C: Green-stemmed *Basella alba* seed; D: Green-stemmed *Basella alba* leaf.

Table 1: Electrophoretic profile of the seed and leaf proteins of the *Basella alba* morphotypes studied

Protein type	Slow bands (0 – 1.9) cm	Intermediate bands (2.0 – 3.9) cm	Fast bands (4.0 – 6.0) cm	Total number of bands	Common bands	Unique bands
Green stemmed seed	1	1	6	8	5	3
Red stemmed seed	1	2	4	7	5	2
Green stemmed leaf	1	1	5	7	6	1
Red stemmed leaf	1	1	6	7	6	1

Five common bands (62.5%) were found between the seed protein of the green stemmed and red stemmed *B. alba* studied at 0.2cm – 0.4cm, 4.3 – 4.8 cm, 4.8 – 5.2, 5.5 cm – 5.8 cm, and 6.0 cm – 6.5 cm (Figure 2). The red stemmed *B. alba* seed protein had 2 unique bands at 2.6 cm – 3.2 cm and 3.6 cm – 4.3 cm, while the green stemmed had 3 unique bands at 2.8 cm – 3.2 cm, 5.2 cm – 5.3 cm, and 6.4 cm – 6.5 cm (Figure 2). The SDS PAGE of the leaf protein also

led to the detection of fifteen (15) bands, two (2) of which were slow moving, three (2) were intermediate, and ten (11) were fast moving (Table 1).

The analysis of the protein bands of the leaf protein revealed that both the green stemmed and the red stemmed *B. alba* had seven (7) bands. Six common bands (85.7%) were found in the leaf protein of the two *B. alba* morphotypes studied at 2.3 – 2.6 cm, 4.5 cm – 4.8 cm, 5.0 – 5.4 cm, 6.0 cm – 6.3 cm, 6.4 cm – 6.5 cm, and 6.5 cm – 6.6 cm (Figure 2). The red-stemmed *Basella alba* leaf had one (1) unique band at 0.2cm – 0.4cm, while the green-stemmed *Basella alba* leaf had one (1) unique band at 0.1cm (Figure 2). The Sokal and Sneath coefficient of similarity revealed 50.0% similarity in the seed protein of the green stemmed and red stemmed *B. alba* studied (Table 2), and 75% similarity in the leaf protein contents (Table 3).

Table 2: Coefficient of similarity of seed protein samples of *Basella alba* morphotypes studied

	Green stemmed seed	Red stemmed seed
Green stemmed seed	–	50.0%
Red stemmed seed	50.0%	–

Table 3: Coefficient of similarity of leaf protein samples of *Basella alba* morphotypes studied

Morphotypes	Green stemmed leaf	Red stemmed leaf
Green stemmed leaf	–	75.0 %
Red stemmed leaf	75.0 %	–

DISCUSSION

Identifying plant taxa using protein banding patterns allows detection of genetic variation that may not be evident from gross morphological characters such as habitat, stems, leaves and flowers, and has been widely applied in plant systematics and diversity studies (Adhikari *et al.*, 2012; Bose *et al.*, 2023). The results of the seed and leaf protein profile, as well as relatively high coefficient of similarity (50% in the seed protein and 75% in the leaf proteins) noted in

this study is a strong indication that a strong degree of similarity exist between the green stemmed and the red stemmed *Basella alba* studied irrespective of their stem colors. The protein profile revealed that most of the protein bands were common bands, with the seed proteins comprising 62.5% common bands and the leaf proteins comprising 85.7% common bands.

The presence of common protein bands between the green stemmed and red stemmed *Basella alba* suggests that the genes coding for these proteins are conserved and may represent adaptive traits that have evolved and become fixed over time. Such common bands support the classification of these morphotypes as the same species and may reflect a shared evolutionary origin (Teniola *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, these bands imply that the proteins they represent have identical amino acid sequences. This suggest that the green stemmed and the red stemmed *B. alba* are possibly not separate species, but morphotypes or varieties of same species, hence supporting the taxonomic classification of the two as same species. This is corroborated by previous reports by other researchers (Roy *et al.*, 2010; Bolaji *et al.*, 2022a, Bolaji *et al.*, 2023) who noted that the green stemmed and the red stemmed *Basella alba* were quite close genetically and are not separate species.

Notably, the presence of unique protein bands in the seed and leaf proteins of the green stemmed and red stemmed *B. alba* points to intervarietal differences between the two morphotypes. Such variations in protein makeup have been widely reported as valuable markers for differentiating and classifying members of a population into appropriate taxonomic groups (Teniola *et al.*, 2021). The unique bands at 2.6 cm – 3.2 cm and 3.6 cm – 4.3 cm in the seed protein of the red stemmed, and at 2.8 cm – 3.2 cm, 5.2 cm – 5.3 cm, and 6.4 cm – 6.5 cm for the green stemmed seed protein, as well as the the unique band at 0.2 cm – 0.4 cm for the red stemmed leaf protein and 0.1cm for the green stemmed leaf protein may be valuable for distinguishing the two morphotypes from each another. Similar findings have been reported in earlier studies (Oladejo *et al.*, 2019; Shonde *et al.*, 2023; Bolaji *et al.*, 2025), supporting the use of unique bands as indicators of genetic differences. Protein electrophoresis has been widely reported as an effective biochemical marker for assessing genetic relationships because differences in band presence and absence correspond to variation in expressed gene products (Abdelhaliem *et al.*, 2023; Bolaji *et al.*, 2025). Such variation can also be useful in crop improvement programmes, as plant breeders can use these differences to select better traits and exploit heterosis for improved crop development (Olanrewaju *et al.*, 2021; Olomitutu *et al.*, 2022, Bolaji *et al.*, 2023; Adeniran and Bolaji, 2024). The predominance of fast moving bands

in the seed and leaf protein of the green stemmed and red stemmed *B.alba* studied implies that the two *Basella* forms consist mainly of proteins with high molecular weight.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed relatively high level of coefficient of similarity between the green stemmed and the red stemmed *Basella alba* studied, with the seed protein having 50% and the leaf protein having 75% similarity, indicating that a strong degree of similarity exist between the green stemmed and the red stemmed *Basella alba* studied irrespective of their stem colors. The study supports the taxonomic classification of the green stemmed and red stemmed *B.alba* as morphotypes or varieties belonging to same species.

Conflict of Interests

There are no conflict of interests before, during or after the work

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